

Privacy and Confidentiality in International Commercial Arbitration: The Tanzanian Approach

Grace Francis Masimini,

Dar es Salaam Tumaani University (DarTU), Tanzania.

Email: gracemasimin5@gmail.com

Abstract:

Privacy and confidentiality lie at the heart of international commercial arbitration. Parties have a fundamental obligation to protect and handle commercial documents and personal information in a way that prevents their exposure to the public or third parties. Generally, there is an overlap between the rules governing the conceptualization and application of privacy and confidentiality in arbitration. Nevertheless, the scope of the duty of confidentiality has remained unclear, and has therefore been increasingly challenged in arbitral proceedings. Whilst other jurisdictions have gone ahead to expressly address these duties within their legal frameworks, the position of the Tanzanian Arbitration Act of 2020 and its implications for international commercial arbitration calls for closer scrutiny. This article examines this issue using the doctrinal research methodology.

Keywords: Confidentiality, International Commercial Arbitration, Privacy, Tanzania.

Suggested Citation: G. F. Masimini (2025), 'Privacy and Confidentiality in International Commercial Arbitration: The Tanzanian Approach,' *East. Af. JLP&G*. Vol. 3. No.1. pp. 1-22.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution

International License (CC BY 4.0).

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant discussions in the arbitration of commercial disputes is the adherence of the proceedings to the rules on privacy and confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality are among the fundamental principles underpinning commercial arbitration. In other words, they lie at the heart of commercial arbitration. These principles are expected to play complimentary roles at the national and international levels because the international legal framework sets a standard for domestic jurisdictions to follow. However, in Tanzania, adherence to the dictates of privacy and confidentiality in arbitration of international commercial disputes require further investigation. This article therefore examines the rules on privacy and confidentiality in the area of international commercial arbitration. It discusses the relevance of the principles and their practicability in the Tanzania.

2. WHY CONFIDENTIALITY AND PRIVACY MATTER IN IN ARBITRAL PROCEEDINGS?

The history of privacy and confidentiality in commercial arbitration dates back to ancient times, with the first signs of arbitration-like mechanisms appearing in the sixth century B.C. Different cultures and ethnic groups united by the city-states of ancient Greece and the Roman Empire knew Arbitration and applied it to political disagreements and territorial disputes.¹ Initially, the two terminologies were used interchangeably to mean the same thing in arbitration until the latter of the 20th century whereas privacy in the arbitration context meant that no third party was allowed to attend arbitral conference and hearings, while confidentiality was referred to as the non-disclosure of specific information in public.²

The duty of confidentiality has always been considered a product of the private nature of arbitration proceedings.³ Some scholars argue that this very notion is controversial to the extent that it fails to distinguish ‘confidentiality’ from ‘privacy’.⁴ Arguably however, only passing reference is made in contemporary text on arbitration laws and institutional rules to the legal definition of confidentiality and to its distinction from the concept of privacy. This distinction is further problematic when privacy and confidentiality are coupled with

¹ G Szalay, ‘A Brief History of International Arbitration, Its Role in the 21st Century and the Examination of the Arbitration Rules of Certain Arbitral Institutions with regards to Privacy and Confidentiality’, 1 [2016] *University of Pecs Journal* at p.07

² See <https://aria.law.columbia.edu/confidentiality-in-international-commercial-arbitration-determining-factor-for-safeguarding-the-legitimacy-of-the-process/> Accessed on July 29, 2024

³ G Weixia., ‘Confidentiality Revisited: Blessing or Curse in International Commercial Arbitration?’ [2005] 15 *Am Rev Intl Arb* at p. 607

⁴ *Ibid* at p. 608.

data protection in arbitration.⁵ This is because they are all separate legal concepts that have been regulated differently by industry-specific rules, and by national and international laws.⁶ The two legal concepts in relation to arbitration are discussed below.

2.1 Privacy in arbitration

Privacy in arbitration implies that only the parties to the arbitration have a right to attend the arbitration proceedings, to the exclusion of third parties.⁷ It goes beyond maintaining secrecy but also protects the arbitral process from external interferences or third parties. Privacy is a major institutional requirement in arbitration.⁸ Although, privacy and confidentiality connote two different things, they are interrelated. Confidentiality in its most basic sense implies that the existence of the arbitration; the subject matter, evidence, documents used, the award and other decisions cannot be divulged to third parties.⁹

Furthermore, it is important for arbitrators to be able to consistently maintain privacy whether at domestic or international for in instances including the submission of documents and in the preparation and issuing of awards. The problem is that privacy is not treated consistently across legal systems and jurisdictions. It varies from being extensively protected in law to receiving no protection, as a privacy right. It is therefore, a challenge for arbitrators to determine the scope of privacy rights as they relate to arbitral hearings and awards. This issue is relevant for the collection of personal information and its transmission to the arbitral tribunal, the parties and tribunal members. It is also the requirement to disclose private information in preparing for, and conducting hearings. The requirement extends to denying third parties, physical access to the hearing; to documentation used in preparation for the hearing, and the ensuing award. However, the parties may consent to the disclosure of information to third parties, or the tribunal may in certain cases order access to the proceedings.

The scope of the legal right to privacy is best determined by how it is defined and applied to arbitration proceedings. In terms of materials, it is how it regulates the transmission of documents to third parties, as well as the right to participate in arbitration proceedings.¹⁰ Individuals, communities, governments, and the general public all have different

⁵ L Trackman., 'Confidentiality, Privacy and Data Protection in International Commercial' Arbitration in Franco Ferrari and Rosenfeld F., (eds). 'Handbook of Evidence in International Commercial Arbitration: Key Issues and Concepts', (Kluwer Law International, 2022). at p. 331.

⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ G Tobing., A Sulistiyono, and H Purwadi. 'Political perspective of law on empowerment of arbitration as institution for settlement of industrial relation disputes.' 45 (9) [2016] *J. Law Policy Globalization* pp. 67–84 at p. 78

¹⁰ H Walker., D Chicksand., Z Radnor., and G Watson., 'Theoretical perspectives in operations management: An analysis of the literature,' 35(8) [2015]. *Int. J. Oper. Prod. Manage* pp. 1182–1206 at p. 1187

concepts of privacy. Unlike other areas of law with well-defined legal concepts, norms, and principles, the meaning of privacy is far from settled.¹¹ Given these divergent attributes of privacy, the question arises over how privacy impacts upon international commercial arbitration. The related question is whether privacy is seen as an extension of confidentiality, or is entirely different from it.¹²

2.2 The relationship between privacy and confidentiality

While it can be argued on one hand that privacy is concerned with the right of persons other than the arbitrators, parties, their representatives and witnesses to attend the arbitral hearing, on the other hand, it may be argued that confidentiality is concerned with ‘information relating to the content of the proceedings, evidence, documents, and transcript of the hearing or the award. Viewed this way, privacy and confidentiality have their own distinct dimensions in arbitration. However, their differences are minimized by highlighting their interconnectedness. Specifically, as highlighted above, confidentiality and privacy share the same purpose of protecting the personal information or data used in arbitration proceedings.¹³ Non-parties, such as public interest organizations, are also denied attendance at the hearings, and are not granted access to documents, hearing transcripts, and the judgment.

Privacy and confidentiality both aim to protect personal data and information as defined and prescribed by law. As a result, the degree of privacy over personal information granted to a party during arbitration is intertwined with the observance of the rules of confidentiality in the procedures followed and the award given.

3. CONFIDENTIALITY IN INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL ARBITRATION

Confidentiality is the corner stone of international commercial arbitration.¹⁴ Accorded a hallowed status in arbitration, confidentiality has been projected as a major reason for which parties choose arbitration over litigation.¹⁵ This section of the paper examines confidentiality in arbitration at the international level and under institutional rules.

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ L Trackman., ‘Confidentiality, Privacy and Data Protection in International Commercial’ Arbitration in Franco Ferrari and Rosenfeld F., (eds). ‘*Handbook of Evidence in International Commercial Arbitration: Key Issues and Concepts*’, (Kluwer Law International, 2022). at p. 329

¹⁴ See N Redfern. & M Hunter., ‘*Redfern and Hunter on International Arbitration*’, (Oxford University Press, 2009). at p. 145.

¹⁵ See W Newman., ‘*The Leading Arbitrators’ Guide to International Arbitration*’, (Juris Publishing Inc., New York, 2008) at p. 663.

3.1 Confidentiality at the international centre for settlement of investment disputes

Most of the disputes that fall under international commercial arbitration are matters relating to investments. The primary framework that regulates such disputes is the International Centre for the Settlement of Investment Dispute Rules which provide for the forum where investment disputes should be resolved. The ICSID provides an avenue where investors can resolve their disputes. Although the ICSID Rules expressly provide for confidentiality, they do not expressly do so for privacy. Both the ICSID Arbitration Rules, and ICSID Conciliation Rules provide Arbitration Declarations forms and Conciliator Declaration forms which impose a duty of confidentiality on the arbitrator or conciliator: “I shall keep confidential all information coming to my knowledge as a result of my participation in this proceeding, as well as the contents of any award by the Tribunal.” Under Rule 34 (1) of the ICSID Arbitration Rules, the deliberations of the Tribunal shall take place in private and remain confidential. Furthermore, under Rule 62 ICSID Rules on Arbitration, the tribunal can only publish the award if the parties to the arbitral proceedings consent to it.

3.2 Confidentiality at the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law, 1985

Confidentiality can be examined under the United Nations Commission on international Trade Law commonly known as UNCITRAL Model Law which binds Tanzania. This instrument which came into force many years after the New York Convention, envisages arbitration as taking place between only parties to a written arbitration agreement.¹⁶ The 1985 UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration provides under Article 7(1) that an arbitration agreement:

Is an agreement by the parties to submit to arbitration all or certain disputes which have arisen or which may arise between them in respect of a defined legal relationship, whether contractual or not. An Arbitration agreement may be in the form of an arbitration clause in a contract or in the form of a separate agreement.

(2) The arbitration agreement shall be in writing. An agreement is in writing if it is contained in a document signed by the parties or in an exchange of letters, telex, telegrams or other means of telecommunications which provide a record of the agreement, or in an

¹⁶ In case of Ad Hoc Arbitration.

exchange of statements of claim and defence in which the existence of an agreement is alleged by one party and not denied by another. The reference in a contract to a document containing an arbitration clause constitutes an arbitration agreement provided that the contract is in writing and the reference is such as to make that clause part of the contract.

The provisions relating to the confidentiality in UNICITRAL are similar to those in the ISCID. The UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules encourage parties who want higher levels of confidentiality to in their arbitral proceedings to expressly address confidentiality in their arbitral agreements or by entering into additional confidentiality agreements. The UNCITRAL Model Clause on Confidentiality which uses can adapt to suit their circumstances provides as follows:

1. Each party shall maintain confidentiality of all aspects of the proceedings, including the existence of the proceedings, all non-public information disclosed by another party in the proceedings, all non-public decisions or awards, [and any decisions or awards that have been proven to have become public unlawfully] with the following exceptions: to the extent that such disclosure is required by legal duty, to protect or pursue a legal right or interest, or in relation to enforcing or challenging awards in legal proceedings before a court or other competent authority, or for the purposes of having, or seeking, legal, accounting or other professional services.
2. The arbitral tribunal and the parties shall seek the same undertaking of confidentiality in writing from all those that they involve in the proceedings.
3. The arbitral tribunal may, upon the request of a party, make orders concerning the confidentiality of the arbitral proceedings and take measures for protecting confidential information.

4. DUTY OF CONFIDENTIALITY IN TANZANIA

Confidentiality in Tanzania is governed by two core legislations, which are the Arbitration Act¹⁷ and the Civil Procedure Code.¹⁸ The discussion in this part focuses on the application of these laws to confidentiality and privacy in international commercial arbitration in Tanzania.

4.1 Confidentiality and Privacy under the Arbitration Act No. 2, 2020

Tanzania enacted a new Arbitration Act Cap 15 of 2020 repealing the Arbitration Act, Ordinance No, 26 of 1931.¹⁹ This legislation applies only to Tanzania Mainland based on the nature of the Union between Tanzania Mainland and Tanzania Zanzibar.²⁰ The legislation ushered in a new legal and regulatory terrain on matters of arbitration in Tanzania. It consolidates all the critical phases of arbitration into a single legal instrument. Furthermore, it introduced clear and elaborate rules of practice governing a wide range of issues such as procedural aspects, composition of the arbitral tribunal, accreditation of practitioners and arbitrators with a view to instill ethical and professional etiquette, and management and operations of the newly envisaged Tanzania Arbitration Centre (TAC), which are crucial components of credible and legitimate arbitration systems.

The legislation aims to enhance alternative dispute resolution mechanisms. One of its strengths is the elimination of ambiguity by clarifying what amounts to domestic commercial arbitration and international commercial arbitration. The scope of the Act is however limited to Tanzania mainland as provided by Section 2 and Section 5(1), save for the specific circumstances covered under Section 13 and 68 of the Act which relate to stay of proceedings and enforcement of an award respectively.²¹

With regard to privacy and confidentiality the Arbitration Act provides a definition of ‘confidential information’ under Section 3, that is, ‘all information that relates to the arbitral proceedings or to an award made in those proceedings including the statement of defense, or other information supplies to the arbitral tribunal by a party or any evidence, whether documentary or otherwise, supplied to the arbitral tribunal or any notes made by the arbitral tribunal of oral evidence or submission given before the arbitral tribunal as well as any rulings or award of the arbitral tribunal.’²²

¹⁷ Cap 15, 2020

¹⁸ Cap 33 R.E. 2019

¹⁹ See Section 96(1) of the Arbitration Act Cap 15 of 2020

²⁰ Mwakaje, S, J., and Mkumbukwa N, S., ‘The New Arbitration Law in Tanzania: An Appraisal of Its Salient Features and Implications for Investment Dispute Settlement’, *Journal of International Arbitration* 39(1) [2022] 129 – 162 at p. 130

²¹ *Ibid.*

²² See Section 3 of the Arbitration Act No. 2 of 2020.

Specifically, the Arbitration Act provides under Section 36A for confidentiality of information. It provides that “every arbitration agreement shall be deemed to provide that the parties and the arbitral tribunal shall not disclose confidential information.” However, this provision does not give absolute protection of confidentiality and privacy of arbitration proceedings because several exceptions for disclosure of confidential information are provided under Section 36A(3) as follows:

- (a) to a professional or other adviser of any of the parties; or
- (b) if both of the following matters apply:
 - (i) the disclosure is necessary—
 - (aa) to ensure that a party has a full opportunity to present the party’s case, as required under arbitration rules as may be prescribed in terms of section 90(3);
 - (bb) for the establishment or protection of a party’s legal rights in relation to a third party; or
 - (cc) for the making and prosecution of an application to a court under this Act; and
 - (ii) the disclosure is no more than what is reasonably required to serve any of the purposes referred to in subparagraph (i); or
- (c) if the disclosure is in accordance with an order made, or a summons issued, by a court; or
- (d) if both of the following matters apply:
 - (i) the disclosure is authorized or required by law; or
 - (ii) the party who, or the arbitral tribunal that, makes the disclosure provides to the other party and the arbitral tribunal or, as the case may be, the parties, written details of the disclosure, including an explanation of the reasons for the disclosure; or
- (e) if the disclosure is in accordance with an order made by—
 - (i) an arbitral tribunal under section 36B; or
 - (ii) the court under section 36C.

4.2 Privacy and confidentiality under the Civil Procedure Code [Cap 33 R.E. 2019]

Confidentiality and privacy of Arbitration proceedings may also be discussed from the perspectives of the Civil Procedure Code. In the Civil Procedure Code, arbitration is a part of the mandatory Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) system which was introduced in Tanzania in 1994.²³ Under this framework, the arbitration proceeding takes a different dimension and approach compared to the one envisaged under the Arbitration Act. Arbitration normally commences after a suit is filed and is still pending in the court. Thus, under the Civil Procedure Code, the arbitration is carried out as part of the court litigation process, where parties are given an opportunity to revisit their disputes and weight up the option to resolve it amicably without taking an adversarial stance. It takes place in the course of the court proceedings and is presided over by the court. Once the parties are not able to settle their disputes amicably, the suit resumes under the normal court litigation process.²⁴

Furthermore, the CPC also has provisions that provide for arbitration. For instance, under section 64 and Order VIIIIC rule 35 of the Civil Procedure Code, it provides that: “Any matter in dispute referred to arbitration under a court order shall be dealt with as provided for under the Second Schedule to this Code.” The Second Schedule of Civil Procedure Code further provides rules regulating arbitration in Tanzania whereas these rules are known as, the Civil Procedure (Arbitration) Rules. These rules are applicable in circumstances where in any suit all the parties interested agree that any matter in difference between them shall be referred to arbitration and that they may, at any time before judgment is pronounced, apply to the court for an order of reference.²⁵

4.3 Confidentiality and privacy in settlement of investment disputes in Tanzania

Most of international commercial disputes that often require arbitration as their mode of dispute resolution are investment-oriented disputes. In Tanzania the governing law is the Tanzania Investment Act. This Act is a creature of the parliament of the United Republic of Tanzania. The Act repeals the Tanzania Investment Act No. 26 of 1997 and setting new dimensions on the investment environment in Tanzania. In this part, the Act grants foreign investors access to settle disputes with the Tanzania Investment Centre (TIC) or the government through arbitration process however, the decision to utilize local or foreign avenues has been left for parties to a dispute to agree mutually.²⁶ The new law promotes

²³ See G.N No. 422/1994

²⁴ *Ibid.*

²⁵ See Mswahela D. B., Makori L. M., (2021). *Principles on Alternative Dispute Resolution*, Mzumbe University Tanzania Press at p. 80

²⁶ See Mwakaje S J., and Mkumbukwa N S., ‘The New Arbitration law in Tanzania: An Appraisal of Its Salient Features and Implications for Investment Disputes Settlement’, *Journal of International Arbitration* 39(1) [2022] 129 – 162 at p.158.

the settlement of disputes amicably through negotiation. Parties are free also free to utilize local and international avenues for dispute settlement at a consensus through arbitration.²⁷

The Act specifically states that the parties are free to settle their disputes in accordance with Tanzania Arbitration laws, in accordance with the International Centre for the Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID) or within the framework of any bilateral or multilateral agreement on investment protection agreed to by the Government of Tanzania and the Government of the country originates.²⁸ This Act refers dispute to follow the default mechanism as enshrined under the Arbitration Act No. 2 of 2020 and in that case with regard to confidentiality the provisions of Section 36A and 36B prevail. The Act emphasizes on the adherence to the party autonomy in choice of the arbitration tribunal. This means in practice if the protection of the duty to confidentiality and privacy is absolute then Tanzania will attract a lot of international commercial disputes be referred to its institutions.

4.4 Confidentiality and privacy under Arbitration (Rules of Procedures) Regulations

This regulation is made under the auspices of Section 90 of the Arbitration Act. These regulations have been articulated with the aim to govern arbitration proceedings, concerning the general conduct of arbitration, conditions for arbitration, notices submissions, the commencements of arbitration proceedings, and the provisions of award and decisions from Arbitrator or Arbitration Centre. The regulations are deemed to form part and parcel of any contract that provides for arbitration as such all arising disputes from such contracts are to be settled in accordance to the regulations.²⁹ The regulations also require and only recognizes arbitrators who are accredited or provisionally registered in terms of the Reconciliation, Negotiation, Mediation and Arbitration (Practitioners Accreditation) Regulation of 2021.³⁰

Moreover, the regulation provides for the qualification of the person(s) to be appointed as arbitrators. Furthermore, under the regulations, an Arbitral tribunal is established if it includes a sole arbitrator or a panel of arbitrators who shall preside over the matter. The regulations also set out a special clause or a standard clause to be incorporated into the contracts of any parties who may wish to resolve their matter through the Arbitration Centre.

²⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ See Rule 3 of the GN No. 146/2021.

³⁰ See Mswahela D. B., Makori L. M., (2021). *Principles on Alternative Dispute Resolution*, Mzumbe University Tanzania Press at p. 79.

Unlike the English Arbitration law,³¹ Tanzania Arbitration in practice does not reflect the UNICITRAL Model Law, 1985. The Arbitration Act was originally enacted in 1931 and modeled on the English law of the time. It is generally not possible to appeal an arbitration award outside the framework of the arbitration agreement.³² However, an arbitrator's award may be challenged by application to the High Court on the grounds of misconduct by the arbitrator and, or improper procurement of the award. The arbitration Act largely remained unchanged, with only minor amendments in the 1971 granting the court power to extent the time for getting arbitration proceeding under way. This allowed the court the authority, in some situations, to enable arbitration procedures to begin after the contractual time set by the parties under the arbitration provision has elapsed. Tanzania's Civil Procedure Code also addressed arbitration when it occurs in the course of judicial proceedings.³³

In Tanzania, arbitration proceedings may commence after court proceedings have already begun and pending. If the parties agree to go to arbitration during the course of court proceedings, the trial court has to give its permission. The court supervises the process and the award must be reported to the court in order to mark the proceedings as formally concluded. If the arbitration is inconclusive, the matter will be resolved as a civil case ordinary litigation.³⁴

With respect to confidentiality as provided under Section 3 and 36A of the Arbitration Act, the protection of confidentiality is still not absolute. There are also no sanctions yet for the breach of confidentiality under the Act or by contract. A vivid example in Tanzania was the case of *Biwater Gauff (Tanzania) Limited v. The United Republic of Tanzania*.³⁵ In this case, the court said that having identified the competing interests of transparency and the need to protect procedural integrity, the Tribunal first held that there was neither any general duty of confidentiality nor any general rule of transparency in the International Centre for settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID) arbitration proceedings. However, the Tribunal found that, given the significant media coverage of this case, there was a sufficient risk of aggravation or exacerbation of the dispute 'to warrant some form of control'.

The tribunal considered each category of documents, balancing both interests of procedural integrity and transparency, and issued an order directing both parties to refrain from disclosing minutes or records of hearings, documents produced by either

³¹ See England Arbitration Act, 1966.

³² S J Mwakaje., and N S Mkumbukwa., 'The New Arbitration Law in Tanzania: An Appraisal of Its Salient Features and Implications for Investment Disputes Settlement'. *Journal of International Arbitration* 39(1) [2022] pp. 129–162 at p. 129

³³ See, Second Schedule of Civil Procedure Code, [Cap 33 RE 2002]

³⁴ See D B Mswahela., and L. M Makori., '*Principles on Alternative Dispute Resolution*', (Mzumbe University Tanzania Press, 2021). at p. 86

³⁵ ICSID Case No. ARB/05/22

party in disclosure procedures, pleadings and correspondence. However, they were free to 'engage in general discussion about the case in public, provided that any of these public discussion is restricted to what is necessary, and is not used as an instrument to aggravate the parties, exacerbate their differences, unduly pressure one of them, or render a settlement of the dispute potentially more challenging, or bypass the terms of this 'Procedural Order'.³⁶ Although the Tribunal suggested that it would be in favor of permitting the publishing of its judgments, orders, and directions, it concluded that it would make a case-by-case ruling upon a party's request for the disclosure of such kind of documents. It held in this regard that Procedural Order No. 3 was subject to no confidentiality restrictions.

Therefore, the United Kingdom's position on implied confidentiality seems to respect the duty of confidentiality as compared to the position in Tanzania. In the latter, it is important for parties going into an international arbitration to be aware of the need to discuss and to lay down in writing any agreement on confidentiality.³⁷ This problem of confidentiality seems to be not settled, it is a time for Tanzania to ensure that they observe the duty of confidentiality if at all they want other states and individuals to arbitrate their disputes in Tanzania. Arbitration hearing by its nature is confidential. This is why many parties opt for arbitration hoping that their case will remain private far away from the eyes of the press. A fair example for instance, is the provision of Section 36A of the Arbitration Act which compels proceedings to be recorded by camera. The challenge with this provision is that it is most likely that neither the arbitrators nor parties from both sides that are familiar with the digital operations as far as recording of proceedings are concerned, and therefore require another person who is neither arbitrator nor party to any of the side to assist and operate the recording process, and storage all these instances tempers this the confidentiality of the dispute.

5. THE BASIS OF CONFIDENTIALITY IN ARBITRATION PROCEEDINGS

An obligation of confidentiality can arise because it is implied by fact into the arbitration agreement or because it is a duty imposed by law or because there are property rights in the information that has been disclosed.³⁸ In *Hyundai Engineering v. Active Building and Civil Construction (pte) Ltd*³⁹ Phillips J., (as he then was), had to consider the question of whether a third party who obtained confidential information within arbitral

³⁶ C J Mashamba., *'Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in Tanzania'*, Law and Practice, (Mkuki na Nyota Publishers, 2014) at p. 125

³⁷ See, United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL), *UNCITRAL Notes on Organizing Arbitral Proceedings*, 31, U.N. Doc. A/CN.9/423 (Oct. 4, 1996).

³⁸ Issues relating to the confidentiality of trade secrets and TRIPS (Agreement on the Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights), Article 39, also see, F Dessemonter, *'Arbitration and Confidentiality'*, available at <http://www.unil.ch.icedac/articles/arbitrationconfidential.pdf> Accessed on May 23, 2024.

³⁹ Judgement delivered 9 March 1994, see (1995) 11 *Arbitration International* (No. 3), 232-3.

proceedings was also under a duty of confidentiality. Phillips J, concluded that the person would be under a duty not to disclose the information but stated that the basis of that duty was not clear, he observed that:

The authorities demonstrate that the nature and extent of the duty of confidentiality applicable to documents and information obtained in arbitration proceedings is by no means fully chartered. It is not clear whether the duty of confidentiality arises out of a contractual term or by virtue of the relationship between the parties.

In another case, *Ali Shipping v. Shipyard Trogir*,⁴⁰ Potter LJ, in the English Court of Appeal, considered the basis on which an obligation of confidentiality was implied. Here Potter LJ, held that a duty of confidentiality was an implied term in the arbitration agreement. Such an implied term was not imposed to give business efficacy to the contract but imposed as a matter of law as a necessary incident of a definable category of contractual relationships.⁴¹ Potter LJ, stated that the way in which confidentiality was approached in arbitration proceedings was by taking a broad principle that confidentiality does attach to such proceedings and then formulating exceptions to the principle. This has been traditional approach of the English courts in considering the basis on which the confidentiality obligation would be imposed.⁴²

However, in the recent case, *Associated Electric and Gas Insurance Services Ltd (AEGIS) v. European Reinsurance Co. of Zurich*⁴³ the Privy Council of England called into question the approach taken in *Ali Shipping v. Shipyard Trogir*. In the *Associated Electric case*, Lord Hobhouse stated that the Privy Council had reservations about the approach of characterizing the duty of confidentiality as an implied term and then formulating exceptions to which it would be subject. Furthermore, Lord Hobhouse stated that: “the approach adopted by Lord Justice Potter, runs the risk of failing to distinguish between different types of confidentiality which attach to different types of documents which have been obtained in different ways...”

Generally, commercial arbitrations are essentially private proceedings and unlike litigation in public courts do not place anything in the public domain. This may mean that the implied restrictions on the use of material obtained in arbitration proceedings may have greater impact than those applying to litigation. But when it comes to the award, the same logic cannot be applied. An award may have to be referred to for accounting

⁴⁰ [1998] 2 All ER 136

⁴¹ See *Scally v. Southern Health Board* [1992] 1 AC 294, 307.

⁴² See, *Insurance Co. v. Lloyd's Syndicate* [1995] 1 Lloyd's Rep 272 at 275 where Colman J, held that the scope of the qualification to the duty of of confidence is implied as a matter of business efficacy.

⁴³ [2003] UKPC 11

purposes or for the purpose of legal proceedings (as Aegis referred to for accounting purposes or for the purposes of the present injunction proceedings) or for the purposes of enforcing the rights which the award confers.

Although the Privy Council was clear that generalizations and the articulation of detailed implied conditions are not acceptable in assessing whether a document is confidential, it did not go on to establish a standard or tests for evaluating how confidentiality emerged in arbitration. This leaves the questions of how an obligation of confidentiality is imposed under English law in a state of flux.

6. CONFIDENTIALITY AS AN IMPLIED OBLIGATION

While in certain jurisdictions such as the UK as it has been discussed already herein in the above parts, but also countries like France and Singapore, the courts have deemed the matter of confidentiality as inherent in the arbitration process and they have treated it as implied obligation. In England for instance, in the case of *Hassaneh Insurance Co. of Israel & ORS v. Stuart J Mew*,⁴⁴ the court had held, confidentiality is implied in all arbitration agreements and must be based upon customary or business efficacy. Further, in another case of *Ali Shipping Corporation v. Shipyard 'Trogir'*,⁴⁵ the court had provided the detailed guideline about the matter of confidentiality.

Giving the lead judgment, Potter L. J. observed in this case that:

I observe by way of preliminary that, to date, the confidentiality rule has been founded fairly and squarely on the ground that the privacy of arbitration proceedings necessarily involves an obligation not to make use of material generated in the course of arbitration outside the four walls of the arbitration, even when required for the use of other proceedings.⁴⁶

He made the following exceptions to the general rule: if a party consents to the disclosure; if the court issues an order or grants permission for the disclosure of such documents or evidence; When it is reasonably required to preserve the legitimate interests of the party to arbitration, and if the interests of justice necessitate disclosure.⁴⁷

⁴⁴ (1993) 2 Lloyd's Rep. 243

⁴⁵ (1998) 2 All E.R. 136

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

⁴⁷ See H Yu, "A theoretical overview of the foundations of international commercial arbitration." 1(2) [2008], *Contemp. Asia Arbitration J.* pp 255–286 at p. 271

On the other hand, countries such as Singapore adopted the English approach as far confidentiality in international arbitration is concerned. This was observed in the case of *Myanma Yaung Chi Oo Co. v. Win Win Nu*,⁴⁸ the court rejected the Australian approach and preferred to adopt English approach of confidentiality in arbitration.⁴⁹ In France on the other limb, in the case of *Aita v. Ojeh*,⁵⁰ Aita was seeking in France, an annulment, of an award which was earlier rendered in arbitration proceeding in London. The court held that it did not have jurisdiction, and that Aita had violated the principle of confidentiality. He was ordered to pay a fine to the other party for the breach of that principle.⁵¹

Confidentiality therefore plays an important role in the area of international arbitration. The English courts have pertinently observed that the confidentiality is an implied obligation arising from agreement to arbitrate. This historical evolution and contemporary purposes of international agreements require this result.⁵² The most parties enter into international agreements with expectations of confidentiality, which are generally perceived as one of the important advantages of international arbitration as a mode of dispute resolution.

Hence, it should be seen with surprise that the recent amendments in the institutional arbitration are coming with enhanced obligations of confidentiality in the arbitration process. Confidentiality in the arbitration is not merely a reflection of an innate feature of the arbitration but it also fulfills the requirement of 'privacy' which is almost universally accepted. In *Esso Australia Resources Ltd & ORS v. Plowman (Minister for Energy and Minerals) & ORS*,⁵³ it was held that, no sharp distinction can be drawn between privacy and confidentiality in this context. There are two sides of the same coin. The privacy of arbitration exists in order to maintain the confidentiality of the dispute which the parties have agreed to submit to the arbitration and any curtailment in the confidentiality will affect the privacy of the arbitrator.

7. EXCEPTIONS TO CONFIDENTIALITY

The duty of confidentiality is not absolute; there are circumstances in which the duty of confidentiality can be waived away. In the landmark case of *Ali Shipping v. Shipyard Trogir (supra)*, Potter L.J, acknowledged that the confidentiality obligation was not absolute and that there were a number of exceptions to that obligation. Absolute confidentiality in arbitral proceedings would result in a paradox. If the parties to arbitration ever sat down and thought about the issue of confidentiality, they would inevitably conclude that neither of them would want a rule that arbitrations were

⁴⁸ [2003] S.L.R 547

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

⁵⁰ Paris, February 18, [1986], 1986 Rev. Arb. 583

⁵¹ *Supra* note 72 at p. 275

⁵² *Ibid.*

⁵³ (1995) 128 A.L.R. 391.

confidential without exception. The parties may need to show the award to insurers or to a parent company. The parties may also want to enforce the award if it is not honored and the only way to do this is in the courts, which will often be a public forum. When the issue of confidentiality was considered in *Ali Shipping's case*, Potter LJ., laid down four exceptions to the confidentiality obligation which are, where a party consents to the disclosure; if the court makes an order or grants leave for disclosure of such documents or evidence; when it is reasonably necessary to protect the legitimate interests of the party to the arbitration;⁵⁴ and where the interests of justice require disclosure. These exceptions to the duty of confidentiality are discussed below.

7.1 Consent of parties to the disclosure

Parties to arbitration can agree to disclose information relating to arbitration proceedings. The laws on arbitration, allows disclose if parties consent. For instance, the consent of the parties can be written into arbitration agreement between the parties, or given after a dispute has arisen in a post-dispute arbitration agreement. The implied consent of the parties can arise from the parties' conduct after a dispute has arisen. One example of this is where an arbitrating party applies to the court for the removal of an arbitrator, in which case that arbitrating party implicitly gives consent to the challenged arbitrator to disclose matters concerning the arbitration to the court. A further question that arises in this context is whether an application to the court arising out of an arbitration, without an arbitrating party asking for those proceedings to be held in camera (assuming such provisions exist in the relevant national court), amounts to a consent to public disclosure of all facts and documents put before the court.

The parties are therefore free to agree that the award or any documents produced or disclosed in the arbitration should be disclosed. The agreement can be made expressly or impliedly.⁵⁵ In *The Hamtun (owners) v. The St. John (owners)*⁵⁶, Peter Gross, held that where there was a custom to refer to awards then this could amount to an agreement to permit disclosure. In this case the court had to consider whether it should refer to other shipping arbitration awards in order to assist it in determining the level of salvage remuneration. The judge concluded that the implied duty of confidentiality was qualified by custom and practice which allowed these types of awards to be disclosed.

7.2 Court's order for the disclosure

In this area, the court will grant an order for the inspection and disclosure of pleadings, written submissions, and the proof of witnesses as well as transcripts and notes of the evidence given in the arbitration in subsequent litigation if it is satisfied that disclosure is

⁵⁴ See *Hassneth Insurance Co. v. Mew* [1993] 2 Lloyd's Rep. 243.

⁵⁵ The right to disclose the award or any document in the arbitration is also recognized even under English law, in limited circumstances.

⁵⁶ [1999] 1 All ER (Comm.) 587.

reasonably necessary either for disposing fairly of the action or for saving costs.⁵⁷ Similarly, leave of the court for disclosure would be given in a number of other limited circumstances. The test to be applied by the court in determining whether to order disclosure would be analogous to that of a banker and client.

Although various cases have recognized the disclosure of arbitration-related documents with leave of court as an exception to the obligation of confidentiality, the question remains as to whether or not a court or tribunal order for disclosure overrides the obligation of confidentiality.

7.3 Protect legitimate interests of the party

The disclosure of arbitration documents for the protection of the legitimate interests of an arbitrating party is clearly a potentially very wide exception. The enforcement of an arbitrating party's rights under an earlier arbitration award would certainly be a disclosure for protecting the legitimate interests of the winning party. Alternatively, a party may wish to disclose an arbitration award to adduce evidence of a position that was taken by an arbitrating party in an earlier arbitration so as to raise issue estoppel.

In *Associated Electric and Gas Insurance Services Ltd. (AEGIS) v. European Reinsurance Company of Zurich*,⁵⁸ a case arising out of two separate arbitrations concerning European Reinsurance's obligation to indemnify AEGIS under a reinsurance agreement, European Reinsurance sought to refer to the arbitration award obtained from the first arbitration in the second arbitration on the basis that the same dispute had been raised on the pleadings in the second arbitration between the same parties. The tribunals for both the first and second arbitrations were different. As there was an express confidentiality agreement between the parties that had been entered into in the course of the first arbitration, AEGIS contended that the award in the first arbitration should not be disclosed to the tribunal in the second arbitration because it would breach the confidentiality of the first arbitration.

AEGIS then secured an ex parte injunction against European Reinsurance to prevent European Reinsurance from referring to the first arbitration verdict, so precluding European Reinsurance from bringing an issue estoppel plea in the second arbitration. European Reinsurance tried unsuccessfully to dismiss the injunction.⁵⁹ European Reinsurance then appealed successfully to the Court of Appeal of Bermuda, and discharged the injunction. AEGIS appealed to the Privy Council and sought to reinstate

⁵⁷ *Ali Shipping Corp. v. Shipyard Trogir*, *supra*, note 5 also *Hassneh Insurance Co. v. Mew*, *supra*, note 15

⁵⁸ [2003] 1 W.L.R. 1041 (P.C.);

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*

the injunction to restrain European Reinsurance from disclosing the arbitral award in the first arbitration to any third party, including the tribunal in the second arbitration.

The issue before the Privy Council was whether, on its proper construction, a confidentiality agreement that the parties had entered into in the first arbitration precluded reliance on the arbitral award in the second arbitration. In dismissing AEGIS' appeal, the Privy Council held that the confidentiality agreement between the parties did not preclude reliance on the arbitral award in the first arbitration. Therefore, the Privy Council was of the view that the principle of issue estoppel meant that the parties to proceedings were bound by an earlier arbitral award on the same issue, and that confidentiality was immaterial. In that context, the Privy Council considered that issue estoppel was 'a species of the enforcement of the rights given by the award just as much as it would be a cause of action estoppel' even though it was a rule of evidence rather than a mechanism for enforcement as such. There is a requirement of reasonable necessity in the application of this exception for disclosure in the protection of the legitimate interests of an arbitrating party.

Again, in *Ali Shipping Corp. v. Shipyard Trogir (supra)*, Potter, L.J. framed this requirement as follows: "disclosure when, and to the extent to which, it is reasonably necessary for the protection of the legitimate interests of an arbitrating party". However, Potter, L.J. also added that: In this context, that means reasonably necessary for the establishment of an arbitrating party's legal rights vis-à-vis a third party in order to find a cause of action against that third party or to defend a claim, or counterclaim, brought by the third party.⁶⁰ In the same case, Potter, L.J. further noted the comments of Colman, J. in *Hassneh Insurance case*, that it was not enough that an award or reasons might have a commercially persuasive impact on the third party to whom they are disclosed, nor that their disclosure would be 'merely helpful, as distinct from necessary, for the protection of such rights,' but went on to qualify the concept of reasonable necessity as he considered that the court should take a rounded view. Potter, L.J. stated that:

When the concept of reasonable "necessity" comes into play in relation to the enforcement or protection of a party's legal rights, it seems to me to require a degree of flexibility in the court's approach. For instance, in reaching its decision, the court should not require the parties seeking disclosure to prove necessity regardless of difficulty or expense. It should approach the matter in the round, taking account of the nature and purpose of the proceedings for which the material is required,

⁶⁰ *Glidepath B.V. v. Thompson (No. 2)*, [2005] 2 Lloyd's Rep. 549 (Q.B. (Comm. Ct.)).

the powers and procedures of the tribunal in which the proceedings are being conducted, the issues to which the evidence or information sought is directed and the practicality and expense of obtaining such evidence or information elsewhere.

One question that arises from Potter, L.J.'s observations above is whether the protection of the legitimate interests of an arbitrating party is only confined to the protection of that arbitrating party's legitimate interests vis-à-vis a third party. Notably, in *Emmott case*, the Court of Appeal did not appear to confine the protection of the legitimate interests of an arbitrating party vis-à-vis a third party only. However, Thomas, L.J. did not state that a third party was necessary to establish this exception: "Use can, however, be made [of arbitration documents] if it is reasonably necessary to protect the legitimate private interests of a party."

Again, in the *Hassneh case*, Colman, J. found that the disclosure of the reasoned award was reasonably necessary for the defendant to establish his causes of action against the placing brokers. However, Colman, J. did not extend the exception to the other documents generated or disclosed in the course of the arbitration, as they were merely the materials which were used to give rise to the award which defined the rights and obligations of the parties to the arbitration. Accordingly, Colman, J. held that the qualification to the duty of confidentiality based on the reasonable necessity for the protection of an arbitrating party's rights against a third party could not be expected to apply to such documents.

7.4 Interest of justice

Information relating to arbitral proceedings can be disclosed if the interest of justice so requires. If a party has given inconsistent evidence in two separate arbitrations, it is clear that the interests of justice would require disclosure of arbitration documents in spite of any obligation of confidentiality. In *London & Leeds*,⁶¹ it was found that an expert valuer in arbitration had given contrary expert evidence in two previous arbitrations. Thus, Mance, L.J. held that, where a witness was proved to have expressed himself in a materially different sense when acting for different sides, that would be a factor which should be brought out in the interests of individual litigants involved and in the public interest. Mance, L.J. therefore held that the duty of confidentiality that the parties in the two previous arbitrations owed to the expert valuer in respect of his evidence in those arbitrations was overridden in the interests of the fair disposal of the proceedings.

It should be noted that if there is an issue of whether the interest of justice is an exception in itself, or whether it is part of a wider public interest. The English courts appear to be

⁶¹ *London & Leeds Estate v. Paribas* [1995] 1 EGLR at pp. 102

divided in their opinion on this. The public interest exception was expressly recognized by Mance, L.J. in *London & Leeds*,⁶² and also by Thomas, L.J. in *Emmott case*.⁶³ However, Potter, L.J. in *Ali Shipping* preferred the 'interests of justice' which he considered to be narrower than the '*public interest*' exception.⁶⁴ Likewise, Collins, L.J. in *Emmott* expressly recognized the interests of justice exception, but only tentatively recognized the public interest exception.⁶⁵ Like the legitimate interests exception, there also seems to be a reasonable necessity requirement for the public interest exception, in that disclosure of arbitration documents subject to an obligation of confidentiality should go no further than is reasonably necessary to achieve the purpose of that public interest in disclosure.

7.5 Public interest

Accordingly, the nature of the arbitration may give the public a legitimate interest in certain aspects of the arbitration. For instance, in the case of *Esso Australia Resources Ltd. v. Plowman (Minister for Energy and Minerals) (supra)*, the arbitration concerned a dispute over a proposed increase in the price of natural gas supplied by the appellant vendors (Esso) to two public utilities, the Gas and Fuel Corporation of Victoria (GFC) and the State Electricity Commission of Victoria (SEC) allegedly due to the imposition of a new tax on gas. GFC and SEC had entered into separate sales agreements with the appellants. Both the GFC sales agreement and SEC sales agreement contained a provision which required the appellants to provide GFC and SEC as buyers of the gas with details of the calculations on the basis of which an increase or decrease in the price of gas was derived.

7.6 Enforcement of an award

Despite institutional provisions banning unauthorized publication of the final arbitral judgment, as well as the common presumption that an arbitral award is secret, the final award is frequently leaked to media and other third parties. Trade journals and arbitration reporters typically delete identifying aspects of the parties from the award language, although such 'sanitation' is frequently ineffectual in maintaining the parties' anonymity. The 'fact of the arbitration' is quite hard to conceal; Thus, when the public is aware that an arbitration is proceeding between two parties and later, an award is granted and published, it is not difficult to link parties with awards.

⁶² *Ibid* at pp. 109.

⁶³ *Emmott v. Michael Wilson & Partners* EWCA [2008] at para. 130.

⁶⁴ *Ali Shipping Corp. v. Shipyard Trogir* [1997] EWCA pp.327–28.

⁶⁵ *Ibid*.

When an award comes before the court of law for enforcement, it becomes a public forum.⁶⁶ While parties may have agreed to arbitrate confidentially and privately, this cannot dictate the position in respect of arbitration claims that are brought before the courts. One countervailing factor that militates against the extension of the implied obligation of confidentiality to court proceedings is the principle of open justice. The public interest in ensuring appropriate standards of fairness in the conduct of arbitrations militates in favor of a public judgment in respect of judgments given on applications under Section 68. As in other areas of court activity, public inspection is desirable as a method of maintaining trust in the courts and making the administration of justice more transparent. Arbitration is an important component of international, commercial, and financial life, and there is a legitimate interest in its administration and operation. A public decision is especially important when it involves legal or practical difficulties that might give future advice to attorneys or practitioners.

It may be concluded that, while secrecy is seen as one of the benefits of arbitration, it is not absolute; there are a few circumstances in which the requirement of confidentiality can be abandoned. However, these exclusions should be handled with extreme caution so that the obligation of confidentiality does not become meaningless.

8. EXCEPTIONS TO CONFIDENTIALITY IN TANZANIA

Specifically, in Tanzania, there are several exceptions to confidentiality in arbitral proceedings. These are deemed as ground to which the confidentiality in international commercial arbitration may be waived. These exceptions are provided under Section 36A(3) of the Tanzania Arbitration Act as follows: to professional or other adviser of any of the parties or if both of the following matters apply, these are; to ensure that a party has full opportunity to present the party's case as required under arbitration rules as may be prescribed in terms of section 90(3) of the Arbitration Act.⁶⁷ Also, for the establishment or protection of a party's legal rights in relation to a third party; for the making and prosecution of an application to a court under this Act. However, the Act warns that the disclosure must not be more than what is reasonably required to serve any of the purpose as enshrined under Section 36A(i) of the Arbitration Act.⁶⁸

Furthermore, the Code of Conduct for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators, Regulations of 2021 imposes the responsibility of confidentiality upon reconciliators, negotiators, and mediators.⁶⁹ However, the regulations provide

⁶⁶ Section 17 (1) of the Tanzanian Arbitration Act provides *inter alia* that an award on a submission on being filed in the court in accordance with this Act shall, unless the court remits it to the reconsideration of the arbitrators or umpire or sets it aside, be enforceable as if it were a decree of the court.

⁶⁷ See Section 36A(b)(aa) of the Arbitration Act No. 2 of 2020).

⁶⁸

⁶⁹ See Rule 4(2) of the Code of Conduct for Reconciliators, Negotiators, Mediators and Arbitrators, Regulations of 2021

exceptions, under which a reconciliator, negotiator, mediator and arbitrator can waive confidentiality in the arbitration proceeding. These exceptions occur when: there is a written consent of the parties; when ordered to do so by the court or otherwise required to do so by law; when the information or document discloses an actual or potential threat to life; in respect of any report that is required to be prepared by the reconciliatory, negotiator, or mediator; where data about reconciliation, negotiation or mediation is for research and education purposes and where parties in dispute are not, not may not reasonably be anticipated to be identified by such disclosure or where the information is otherwise available to the public. The challenge with this provision is that it expressly mentions only reconciliators, negotiators and mediators but does not mention arbitrators. However, it is desirable to clearly include arbitrators because the duty to maintain confidentiality applies to international commercial arbitration as well. And the lacuna impinges on the performance of the duty.

9. CONCLUSION

To summarize, as noted above, tribunal proceedings are always required to be carried *in camera* to maintain confidentiality of parties' information. This is because confidentiality is a key principle in arbitration which means that the parties and arbitral tribunal must maintain confidentiality of all information and documents related to the arbitration. This principle is well known a 'private justice' and is a fundamental feature of arbitration as it allows parties to resolve their dispute in a private and confidential manner unlike traditional court proceedings where hearings are mostly carried in open court and court documents are generally available to the public. Arbitration proceedings are required to be conducted in private.

Privacy and confidentiality are simultaneously essential principles to maintain the integrity of the arbitration process and to encourage parties to participate in it. Privacy and confidentiality allow parties to speak openly and freely, without fear that they will be used against them outside the arbitration. Furthermore, the confidentiality of arbitration can also be an advantage in business disputes as it allows the parties to avoid publicity, especially negative publicity that could harm their reputation or relationship with customers.⁷⁰ Privacy and confidentiality are significant features of international commercial arbitration. However, parties to arbitral proceedings can go a step further by drafting their own arbitration clause which will reinforce the duties of privacy and confidentiality rather than relying exclusively on international rules.

⁷⁰ J Yesaya, 'Arbitration in Tanzania: Legal Framework and Practice, *Journal on Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR)*